

INCREASING TRENDS OF MIGRATION AMONG THE PUNJABIS

Dr Anupam Bahri

Associate Professor, UILS, Panjab University, Chandigarh

Paper Received On: 20 JULY 2025

Peer Reviewed On: 24 AUGUST 2025

Published On: 01 SEPTEMBER 2025

Abstract

Throughout history migration across international borders has been a significant event. But in recent years it has crosses all the magnitude and direction. Especially in Punjab, a veteran of migratory trends has been witnessed. These changing petters has been effecting people form all phases of life. International migration has been associated with acute events manifested in long term patterns which making it difficult to predict the trends and patterns pertaining to a particular geographical region with any precision. Young people migrate for a plethora of reasons. Some major reasons for migration are found to be to obtain higher education, finding and starting work, or getting married etc. Many youths also choose or are forced to migrate to escape from poverty, violence, conflict, or other displacement are due the effects of war or climate change. As per recent reports youth are heavily represented in migration for humanitarian reasons, including as refugees, asylum-seekers, and as unaccompanied minors. The present paper is mainly focus on all these issues of Punjab.

Key Words: *Migrants, youth, Human Rights, Discrimination*

Introduction

Migration is a result of the uneven distribution of opportunities over a space. People tend to move from places of low opportunity and low safety to places of higher opportunity and better safety. This, in turn, creates both benefits and problems for those areas. Consequences of which can be observed in economic, social, cultural, political and demographic terms.

Definitions of Migration

A migrant is a person who is moving from one place to another. Someone may be considered a migrant regardless of a person's legal status, the cause of migration (voluntary or involuntary), or how long they intend to stay.

Another term for global migration is international migration. This type of migration occurs when people cross state boundaries and stay in a host state for a certain amount of time. People

migrate (move) across the globe, either voluntarily or involuntarily (forced). With the latter, the movement is not of the person's own will, where people may be forced to migrate from conflict or natural disaster.

The geographical definition of migration is the movement of people across a specified boundary to establish a new permanent or semi-permanent residence.

- Global migration refers to the international movement of people across borders, either voluntary or involuntary. There are 3 types of migrants are asylum seekers, economic migrants, and refugees.

According to the World Economic Forum (WEF), India is the top source of international migrants. It terms India as a migration superpower. Migration from India occurs due to so What is Migration?

- When a person or a group of the community moves from one place to another, majorly across political and administrative borders; it gives rise to migration.
- The term migration refers to the movement of people from one area to the other or from one country to another.
- The rate of migration affects the growth of the population of a region by increasing or decreasing the number of people living there.
- Migration can be called permanent, temporary, and daily.

Types of Migration

Migration can be of various types:

- Temporary
- Permanent
- Voluntary
- Permanent

Technically, it is also categorized into the following:

- Counter-urbanization.
- Emigration
- Immigration
- Internal migration
- International migration and
- Rural-urban migration

History of Punjab Migration

In the present scenario migrating abroad is a trending phenomenon among Punjabi youths. Thousands of Punjabi youth are migrating to various foreign countries every year in search of better employment opportunities, better living, and better prospects. Among all these foreign countries, the Canada is their prime destination. Due to Canada's flexible immigration policy the number of migrations from Punjab are on a rise. Most of the migrants who go to Canada are students and they go to Canada to pursue higher education. Besides study visas the other ways they follow are tourist visas and spouse visas to reach Canada. However the startling fact is Canada is not a new destination for Punjabi migrants. Migration from Punjab to Canada started in the last decade of the 19th century. In 1897, a group of Punjabi soldiers under the leadership of Major Kadar Khan travelled through various Canadian cities, including Ottawa, Montreal, and Vancouver, on their way back to India after participating in the Diamond Jubilee celebrations of Queen Victoria held in London. Most of these soldiers were from Punjab and related to agricultural occupations. During this visit, they were fascinated by the vast plains of Saskatchewan, Alberta, and British Columbia. When they returned to Hong Kong, they narrated tales of these vast stretches of land and the great employment opportunities available in Canada to their fellows. The Punjabi soldiers of Hong Kong regiments of the Indian British army again visited Canada when they were on their way to England to participate in Edward VII's coronation ceremony in 1902 (Kazimi, 2011).

The tradition of migration started long before Indian independence and there was a considerable presence of the Punjabi diaspora, from the UK to Canada to China. There are similarities as well as differences between the international migration from Punjab, and the overall international migration from India. And yet there are differences too.

The first wave of migration occurred prior to India's independence that is in 1947 and was primarily driven by two factors, one is indentured labour, and the other is military service. Those who migrated as soldiers were serving in the British Indian Army especially during both the world wars and migrated to countries such as Germany, Italy, Canada, the UK, and the US etc. This wave was important because it gave the Punjabi community an entry point to migrate overseas and head start in terms of migration which is called something a first-runner's advantage.

The second wave of migration occurred immediately after India's independence in 1947 because of combination of economic upheavals and political instability. The newly independent Indian economy was struggling with high levels of poverty and unemployment

etc. Many Punjabis, particularly those from rural areas saw migration to escape poverty and find better economic opportunities abroad. This wave of migration was characterized by a significant degree of unskilled labour migration, with many Punjabis taking up low-wage jobs in countries such as the United Kingdom and Canada.

The third wave of migration occurred during the period of political instability that characterized the state of Punjab beginning in the 1980s to the late 1990s. This era was marked by political unrest, police brutality, and economic challenges, which led many Punjabis to seek new opportunities and better lives abroad for safe and environment and high standard of living.

The fourth wave of migration was also there which began in the late 1990s and continues to the present day. A new set of motivations and drivers characterize this migration. Of course, economic factors continue to play an important role along with many Punjabis seeking better job opportunities and higher wages abroad. However, this wave of migration is also motivated by a range of political and social factors which include political instability, family factors, peer pressure, and concerns about safety and security. This wave of migration is also marked by a significant number of Punjabis seeking permanent residency and citizenship abroad, with many pursuing family reunification and other forms of legal migration.

Push and pull factors for migration.

Migrants throughout the world move for several reasons. Migrations are made not only due to economic factors but also because of the man-made disasters, due to poverty and lack of human development, gender inequalities, discrimination, abuse and neglect, gang violence, political instability, socio-ethnic tensions, bad governance, food insecurity, environmental degradation, and climate change etc. This paper trying to find and analyses the push and pull factors that promote and influence migration in Punjab. The push factors are linked to the place of origin, while the pull factors are linked to the place of destination. For the sake of convenience and analysis, the push-pull factors have been divided into three categories.

a. Economic: One of the primary reasons for the majority of population migration from one country to another is the search for better economic opportunities. Key economic factors influencing overseas migration include employment opportunities, wage differentials, and cost of living. People are inclined to migrate to countries with better job prospects and higher employment rates. Wage differences between countries also drive migration, with individuals seeking higher wages in nations with higher income levels. Remittances play a role as well, as people often migrate to countries with stronger currencies to maximize the value of the money

they send back home. Additionally, the cost of living is a crucial factor, with people tending to migrate to countries where living expenses are lower.

b. Political: Political factors also play a very crucial role in influencing overseas migrations. Political instability, persecution, and human rights violations are one category of forces that cause individuals to flee their home countries in search of safety and protection. Other political factors such as civil wars, armed conflicts, and terrorism can create dangerous and volatile environments, leading people to migrate to more stable and secure countries. However, for the case of this research the domain of which restricts to the state of Punjab, political reasons link to factors such as satisfaction with government policies, human rights violations, government policies, etc.

c. Social: Social factors can also influence overseas migration. Individuals may move to other countries to reunite with family members who have already migrated or to be closer to relatives, a phenomenon known as "family migration." Social networks and connections in destination countries also play a role in migration decisions. For instance, people might choose to migrate to countries where they have friends or family who can provide support and assistance in settling in. Cultural and linguistic factors are significant as well; people are more likely to migrate to countries where their community has already settled, creating a safety net for new migrants. Education and social mobility are other important considerations. Individuals often migrate to countries with better educational opportunities, such as highly ranked universities, to acquire skills and knowledge that can enhance their job prospects and social mobility. Parents may also migrate to offer better educational opportunities for their children. Additionally, other social factors influencing migration include popular narratives, family and "chain" reasons, availability of information, and peer pressure.

1. High Unemployment: Lack of employment opportunities not only in the region of Punjab but in India as a whole is the major push factor that encourages migration of youth to developed countries.
- o Increasing Population: Increase of Population and less increase in facilities as compared to increase in population is also a major factor that causes migration. Population of Punjab is increasing day by day due to which people are forced to work at low wages in order to at least earn something.
- o Strong tradition of emigration: Nobody will disagree that in recent few years there is a trend especially in Punjab to migrate abroad. The lifestyle in foreign countries is much better than the lifestyle of people in Punjab. This better lifestyle and currency difference attracts people to migrate to foreign countries and lead a lavish life with wholesome of facilities.

2. Lack of MNC's in Punjab: Thousands of students in Punjab complete their degrees in business administration every year but due to lack of Multi National Companies & corporate houses in Punjab, they find foreign job opportunities more attractive.
3. Better Education facilities: Education facilities are better in developed countries as compared to India. By studying abroad, students have the opportunity to study in a foreign nation and take in the allure and culture of a new land. Students usually migrate for attaining the chance to experience different styles of education.
4. State government policies: State government policies are very inappropriate and pose a great burden on the people especially business class. If you are an entrepreneur or a businessman, then most of the profit is paid to the government in the form of wealth tax. If you are earning Rs 100/-, then Rs 98/- of your earning is paid to government in form of tax and you are only left with Rs 2/- as profit. This leftover profit is insufficient for future growth and development which in turn forces entrepreneurs to shift to other countries.
5. Less industrial development: Jobs in the government sector are not easily available and Punjab has not seen any major industrial development as well. Whatever industry had been there in cities like Amritsar, Batala, Jalandhar, Ludhiana and Mandi Gobindgarh were also lost during militancy years when established industrialists moved out of the state. On both the agriculture and industrial fronts, there have been no major visible efforts by any successive governments in Punjab which could usher in major development. As a result of the decline in employment opportunities and the reluctance of the youth to engage in agricultural activities, the efforts by the youth to go out increased.
6. Availability of jobs (skilled and unskilled): most of the youth is migrating from Punjab for better job prospects. Jobs whether skilled or unskilled are available easily in the developed countries as compared to India. Even the salary/ wages that are paid there are at a much high rate as compared to India.
7. Family and kinship network: At least 40% of the population of Punjab is settled abroad in developed countries. To join the family and kinship network in these countries is also a major reason for the migration of youth from Punjab.
8. High standard of living and educational opportunities: Better Education facilities and high standard of living is also a major reason for migration abroad. Education at international level is widely considered to add a greater value to one's life. Post

pandemic, this trend seems to have gained traction. Independence, a high standard of living, new cultures, and customs usually attract students to pursue studies abroad.

c. Demographic Factor: The differences in the population growth rates of the different region of a nation have been found to be a determinant in the internal migration. Fertility and the natural increase in population are generally higher in rural areas which drift the population towards the city. Other important demographic factor in internal migration is marriage because females are used to follow their spouses.

Better Public Service and Political environment: Better public service and political environment is also an important factor that explains migration to developed countries. It can be seen that people left their previous places because they were dissatisfied with level of municipal service, public transportation and felt no safety.

Some of the general pull factors other than the above are:

- Better quality of life and standard of living
- Varied employment opportunities, higher wages
- Better healthcare and access to education services
- Political stability, more freedom
- Better life prospects
- For retirees there is a range of services to cater to their needs, or environmental characteristics, such as the coast.

There are various factors which are responsible for migration of unskilled and unemployed workers of India. The main factors are:

- Lack of employment and income-generating opportunities in their areas.
- Food insecurity due to low agricultural productivity.
- Poverty and starvation.
- Income maximization via better job opportunities in these areas.
- Inequitable distribution of benefits of economic development.
- Children's future and more demand for labour in outside countries.

Majorly the push factors are those that force people to leave their place of residence or origin.

Push factors may include:

- Poverty and hunger are one of the main reasons for push factors of migration.
- When people do not find a means of livelihood in their home villages, they are pushed out to the nearby or distant towns.

- Political disturbances and inter-ethnic conflicts drive people away from their homes.
- Migration is the movement of people from one place in the world to another for the purpose of taking up permanent or semi-permanent residence.

When did this influx of migrants start in Punjab?

This trend of migration began in the early 1970's as the Green Revolution took hold. Initially, migrants came to rural areas for paddy sowing and later they also started working in factories. A survey was conducted by parvasi wing of the SAD-BJP government in 2016 and the estimated population of migrants at that time was 39 lakh. Over the years, this has increased to nearly 43 lakh, as revealed by Ram Chander Yadav, president of the parvasi wing of the SAD. Yadav was parvasi wing chief when the survey was conducted in 2016.

Punjab present Scenario

Number of Migrants: Punjab data was reported at 13,735,616.000 Person in 03-01-2011. This records an increase from the previous number of 9,189,438.000 Person for 03-01-2001.

Census: Number of Migrants: Punjab data is updated decadal, averaging 9,189,438.000 Person from Mar 1991 to 03-01-2011, with 3 observations. The data reached an all-time high of 13,735,616.000 Person in 03-01-2011 and a record low of 6,960,431.000 Person in 03-01-1991.

Census: Number of Migrants: Punjab data remains active status in CEIC and is reported by Office of the Registrar General & Census Commissioner, India.

The Majha region of Punjab, which includes the border districts of Gurdaspur and Tarn Taran, witnessed the highest (20.51%) volume of migration followed by Malwa (14.28%) and Doaba (11.27%) An in-depth study conducted by Punjab Agricultural University (PAU), Ludhiana, on the emigration patterns in Punjab has revealed that Canada continues to remain the most preferred destination for Punjabis followed by Dubai and Australia. Canada (41.88%) was the most preferred destination for Punjabis followed by Dubai (16.25%), Australia (9.63%), Italy (5.54%), UK (3.49%), US (3.25%) and others (19.98%), the study found.

The study, the first of its kind covering 44 villages from 22 districts, has also found that 13.34% rural households had at least one family member abroad. Females (65%) outnumbered males (35%) in obtaining study visas as they were able to secure the required IELTS bands. The groundbreaking research, "A Study on Overseas Migration from Rural Punjab: Trends, Causes, and Consequences," led by Professor Shalini Sharma, Professor Manjeet Kaur, and Assistant Professor Amit Guleria from PAU's Department of Economics and Sociology, reveals that the Majha region of Punjab, encompassing the border districts of Gurdaspur and Tarn Taran, has

experienced the highest rate of migration at 20.51%. Following closely are Malwa at 14.28% and Doaba at 11.27%.

Noteworthy hotspots include Amritsar, Shaheed Bhagat Singh Nagar (Nawanshahr), Gurdaspur, and Ferozepur, all with migration rates surpassing 30%. One of the researchers professor Manjeet Kaur said that study was conducted from 2021 to 2023 at the budget of Rs 2.04 lakh to “enumerate the extent of overseas migration in Punjab.”

“Of the total 9492 households in 44 selected villages across 22 districts, we interviewed 640 migrant households (MHs) and 660 non-migrant households (NMHs). A total of 831 migrants from 640 households have been covered in the study. The migration period considered for the study was 1990 to 2022. We found that 13.34% households have at least one migrant family member. It was inferred that migration witnessed a stark increase since 2016 i.e. 74 per cent of total emigration,” she said.

The study has also revealed the sad saga of the financial burden that families had to face to send their loved ones abroad. The study reveals that families have spent Rs 18-25 lakh each on study visa and up to Rs 4 lakh each on work visa, spouse visa or PR. Some also spent Rs 25 to 32.50 lakh on migrants who went by illegal means.

At least 19.38% of migrant families sold their assets, including land, plots/houses, topsoil, cars, gold, and tractors. The average value of assets sold by migrant households was estimated at Rs. 1.23 lakh per household. The analysis revealed that the preferred item to sell among all categories of migrant households was gold. The majority of low-caste, landless, and labour households with low income resorted to selling gold. Around 18 percent of small farm households and less than six percent of medium and large farm households sold land to send their wards abroad.

Of those who sold their gold assets, 28.42% were SCs, 35% were landless, 17% were small farmers and 32% had low income (less than Rs 2 lakh). The low income farmers also sold their tractors to send children abroad, reveals the study.

“Going by the figures of assets sold by families to send their children abroad, it is estimated to be Rs 5636 crore for the entire state. The majority of low-caste, low-income, landless, and laborers migrant households sold houses and gold ornaments to meet the expenses of migration. About 56 per cent of households borrowed money for sending their wards abroad. The average amount borrowed by migrant households worked out to Rs 3.13 lakh per household. Of this, non-institutional borrowing constituted 38.8 per cent and institutional money formed 61.2 per

cent. At the state level, about Rs 14,342 crore were borrowed for the purpose of migration,” said Kaur.

When asked about the reasons for migration, the people interviewed cited low income, lack of employment opportunities (72%), corruption and systemic problems (62%), drug prevalence (52%), social insecurity (50%), small land holdings (35%), landlessness (28%), and debt (24%). The study also revealed that males, landless, minimally educated and SCs from Doaba emigrated to UAE on work visa, while Canada and Australia (via study visa) were the dream destinations for the young as well as Jatt Sikhs from all farm size categories from Majha and Malwa.

71.88% of migrant households and 52.88% of non-migrant households were engaged in agriculture. Among male migrants, 43.15% went on work and 33.73% on study visa while among female migrants 64.37% went on study visa and 14.98% on spouse visa.

At least 95% migrants and 91% families of migrants said they were satisfied with the decision to migrate abroad from Punjab of which 37% said they got better employment, 24% expressed happiness over raised standard of living and 19% were happy with better governance.

Besides finances, migration carried a huge social cost in the form of loneliness (52%), neglect of elderly (41%), indebtedness (38%), abandoned agriculture and parental occupation (30%), and sale of landholdings and assets (26%).

Among suggestions received to stop brain drain from Punjab, 96% said that the status of employment should be improved, 27% said that loopholes in the system should be plugged and citizens should be ensured safety, 21% said that agriculture should be made more viable and 8% demanded better education in government institutes.

The figures for the entire state, including Rs 14300 crore borrowed for migration and assets worth Rs 5,600 crore sold, have been calculated by multiplying average data with 4.58 lakh (i.e. 13.34% of total 34.34 lakh rural households in Punjab), said Kaur.

The basic Rights provided by Convention on the Migrant Workers (2003) in India

The Convention on Migrant Workers (2003) while reaffirming and complementing existing human rights instruments, has forged new grounds and placed human rights in the specific context of migrant rights. As its salient feature, the Convention protects all migrant workers and members of their families, irrespective of their legal status. Nevertheless, the rights granted to documented and undocumented workers are not identical.

Accordingly, the rights of migrant workers and members of their families are set forth in the Convention under two main divisions: those applicable to all migrant workers irrespective of

their legal status (part III) and those applicable to migrant workers in a regular situation (part IV).

Below is a brief list of these rights.

I. Human Rights of Migrant Workers and Members of their Families:

Basic Freedoms:

- Right to freedom of movement to and from their countries of origin (article 8);
- Right to life (article 9);
- Right to freedom from torture or cruel, inhuman or degrading treatment or punishment (article 10);
- Right to freedom from slavery, servitude or forced compulsory labor (article 11);
- Right to freedom of thought, expression, conscience and religion (articles 12 and 13);
- Right to privacy (article 14);
- Right to property (article 15);

Due process:

- Right to a fair and public hearing with all the guarantees of a due process (articles 16-20);
- Right to be provided with necessary legal assistance, interpreters and information in an understood language (article 16);
- Right to liberty and security and freedom from arbitrary arrest or detention (article 16);
- Right to be presumed innocent until proved guilty (article 19);
- Prohibition to be subject to measures of collective expulsion (article 22);
- Right to have recourse to diplomatic or consular assistance and protection (article 23);
- Right to recognition everywhere as a person before the law (article 24);
- Right to equality with nationals before the courts and tribunals (article 18);

Employment:

- Right of equal treatment with nationals in respect to remuneration and other conditions of work such as overtime, holidays, etc. (article 25);
- Right to join freely any trade union (article 26);
- Right to enjoy the same treatment as nationals regarding social security benefits in so far as they fulfill the legislation requirements (articles 27);
- Right to emergency medical care (article 28);

Family and Children of Migrant Workers:

- Right to a name, registration of birth and nationality (article 29);

- Right of access to education (article 30);

Cultural and Economic Rights:

- Right to preserve a cultural identity (article 31);
- Right to transfer earnings and savings upon the termination of their stay in the State of employment (article 32);

Information:

- Right to information by the State of origin, State of employment, or the State of transit of their rights arising from the present Convention, the conditions of their admission, and their rights and obligations in those States (article 33):

II. Other Rights of Migrant Workers and Members of their Families Who Are Documented or in a Regular Situation:

Migrant workers and members of their families who are documented or in a regular situation shall enjoy the rights set forth below in addition to those already mentioned. In such a way, the Convention seeks to discourage illegal migration.

Temporary Absences:

Right to be temporarily absent, for reasons of family needs and obligations, without effect on their authorization to stay or work (article 38);

Freedom of Movement:

Right to liberty of movement in the territory of the State of employment (article 39);

Employment:

- Right to form associations and trade unions in the State of employment (article 40);
- The right to equality of treatment with nationals in respect of protection against dismissal, unemployment benefits and access to alternative employment (article 54);
- In case of violations of work contracts by the employer, the right to address his/her case to the competent authorities of the State of employment.

Political Rights:

- Right to participate in the public affairs of the State of origin, in accordance with its legislation (article 41);
- Right to vote and to be elected in the State of origin, in accordance with its legislation (article 41);

Cultural and Economic Rights:

- Right to enjoy from export and import taxes (article 46).

- The right to equality of treatment with nationals of the State of employment, including access to educational, vocational and social services (article 43);

Conclusion

Migration is not seen so much as employment-driven but as part of them relocating to places where their spouse get jobs. This is why, perhaps, they are invisible when discussing the problems that migrant workers are facing. Even though women enter the workforce in the areas they migrate to, the main reason many of them cite for migration is marriage. In the forced migration that happened last year and is re-emerging now, as in most disasters, there is an unequal gender impact which should be dealt equally with immigrant effects.

National and local laws and policies should be evolved to guarantee that human rights, including labour rights, are enjoyed equally by men and women migrant workers and that migration legislation, policies and programs must promote equality of opportunity and treatment in respect of employment and occupations with a view of eliminating any discrimination based on sex.

Therefore, policymakers and other stakeholders in every country must adopt a gender-sensitive and rights-based approach in developing labour migration laws and policies in line with the core human rights treaties and in particular the Convention on the Elimination of all Forms of Discrimination Against Women, and the Committee on Migrant Workers (CMW), as well as relevant ILO labour standards.

These human rights instruments relevant to migrants seek to achieve gender equality and protection for women and girls irrespective of age, sexuality, race, disability, migration status and other identity markers.

The convention sets out the best strategy to prevent abuses and address challenges faced by migrant workers. It provides guidance for elaborating national migration policies for international co-operation based on respect for human rights and the rule of law.

In addition to setting minimum obligations for the protection of migrant workers and members of their families, the convention is a helpful tool for governance of migration. The convention explicitly provides a framework for human-rights based policymaking on migration, including irregular migration and female migrant workers.

The treaty body of the convention, the CMW, seeks to encourage its state parties and all stakeholders to work towards reaching the standard enunciated in this convention and other relevant international instruments. And CMW in its general comments have elaborated

guidance as to how states can implement their obligation with respect to migrant domestic workers females.

CMW regularly advises states to ensure that they develop effective pre-departure and awareness-raising programs for female workers who have made the decision to migrate, with briefings on their rights under the relevant human rights treaties in force, including CMW, as well as the conditions of their admission and employment and their rights and obligations under the law and practice of the receiving states.

Among other measures, CMW encourage countries of origin to enter into agreements with states of destination for the establishment of standard, unified and binding employment contracts with fair, full and clear conditions and labour standards that are enforceable by systems of law in countries of origin and employment; and to ensure that consular offices are trained to assist female migrant workers, and to provide counselling and guidance for submitting complaints; and encourage states to regulate and monitor recruitment agencies to ensure that they respect the human and labour rights of women migrant workers.

CMW also advises states to repeal sex-specific bans and discriminatory restrictions on women's migration on the basis of age, marital status, pregnancy or maternity status, including restrictions that require women to get permission from their spouse or male guardian to obtain a passport or to travel or bans on women migrant workers.

The issue of detention of female migrant workers is yet another punitive measure that is often abused by authorities in many countries. The convention attempts to make migration for work a positive and empowering experience for individuals and their societies, contributing to economic progress and human development both at home and in destination countries.

Today's dramatic migration crisis underscores the urgent need to begin a more honest discussion about the obstacles to ratification of the Migrant Workers Convention. The convention at present has only 50 state parties, and most are states of origin of migrant workers, and destination countries by not ratifying the convention are conspicuously avoiding the human rights standards of the convention.

Migration is a complex phenomenon that is dealing with overlapping issues relating to the human rights of migrants, mixed migration flows, national wise protection, smuggling and trafficking, as well as other push and pull factors affecting migration but the need of the hour now a days is rights-based comprehensive approach placing the human rights of migrants at the center of the discussion to halt and roll back overall deterioration of treatment of migrant workers in all over world in particularly the women migrant workers and children.

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